

AI4

D5.2 First release of experiment centric and composite-AI tools

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a Demonstrator Deliverable showcasing the status of the WP5 Experiment Centric and Composite AI tools, at the time of the First AI4EOSC software Platform release (AI4EOSC 1). We present the status of the current components and outline the future development directions. By going through the completion status of the Roadmap outlined in Deliverable 5.1, we conclude that the current development of the components is very well aligned with our initial plans.

1 - INTRODUCTION

1.1 - SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

In this document we will go through the components developed in the WP5, “Experiment centric AI services”, at the time of the AI4EOSC First Platform release [ai4eosc]. In Figure 1 we provide an overview of how the different components of WP5 are integrated in the overall platform architecture. As can be seen in the Figure, WP5 components are intended to act as a layer between users -managed in WP6- and base resources (ie. the Nomad cluster, OSCAR) - managed in WP4-, enabling user to have a friendlier experience with the platform.

Figure 1: WP5 tasks and components, in yellow, in the context of the project.

1.2 - STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document goes through all the different components, first introducing the component and its relation to the platform. Then it describes the component evolution since the start of the project and its current features. We finish by briefly discussing what is the expected evolution for each of the components.

In the following section, we evaluate how the current status of the components aligns with the Roadmap described in Deliverable D5.1 [\[D5.1\]](#).

We finally provide conclusions.

2 - EXPERIMENT CENTRIC AI SERVICES

Experiment centric AI solution consists of a comprehensive workplace (suite) designed to streamline the entire machine learning lifecycle, emphasizing a focus on experiment tracking and iterative model development.

2.1 - AVAILABLE COMPONENTS

We will go through the main features of these components. More in-depth information on how to use them can be found in the official AI4EOSC documentation [\[ai4-docs\]](#).

2.1.1 - Platform API

The Platform API [\[ai4-papi\]](#) provides a single entrypoint to access components of the platform. It is a REST API and leverages the OpenAPI specification [\[OpenAPI\]](#). It hides the intrinsic complexity of the underlying technologies used and provides developers with a simple interface to test the services, while building their components or solutions. Hiding the underlying technology gives us flexibility to change the technology used by any component without disrupting neither users, developers, nor the functionality of other components. As an example, the AI4EOSC Dashboard (explained in Section 2.1.2), which is the primary user of the API, is agnostic to the fact that Nomad [\[Nomad\]](#) is currently used as cluster orchestrator. This classical modular approach is important for the robustness of the platform.

The API has been developed from scratch in Python using FastAPI [\[FastAPI\]](#). It is REST compliant and automatically generates a Swagger interface to interact with its endpoints (see [Figure 2](#) for details).

Figure 2: Swagger UI of the API: (left) overview (right) detail of the deployment creation endpoint.

We have deployed both a development instance, where integration tests with the Dashboard are performed, and a production one, where the new functionalities are released to production [ai4-papi]. Both of them have their respective Docker images hosted in the project container registry [ai4-registry] and are deployed via Docker Compose.

The API is currently organized around two main routes: “/catalog” and “/deployments”. In turn, each one of them has the same subpaths dedicated to AI modules (e.g. an image classifier) and for tools (e.g. the federated server).

The “/catalog” route handles all the functionalities to get information about AI modules (and tools). One can:

- get a list of all modules available, filtering by module tag,
- get all the information of a module (name, title, summary, tags, etc),
- get all the parameters needed to configure a deployment of that module.

The “/deployments” route handles the functionality to manage deployments of AI modules (and tools) in the Nomad cluster. One can:

- get a list of all current deployments,
- create a deployment,
- delete a deployment.

The creation of deployments is done by filling predefined Nomad job templates based on the requirements submitted by the user (CPU, GPU, RAM, disk, Nextcloud configuration, deployment title and description, etc). It automatically handles the creation of HTTPS domains for the different module services (deepaas, IDE, monitoring). In addition, we create sidecar tasks in the Nomad jobs that allow real-time data synchronization with the project’s Nextcloud storage [ai4-storage], completely transparent to users.

In the case of the Federated Learning server tool, the API also handles FL configuration (strategy, rounds, etc), as well as the configuration of the deployment's gRPC connection needed to connect to the server. We have also created a route to manage user secrets in Vault [\[Vault\]](#). This will enable users to list/create/update/delete secrets in their Vault containers based on their existing OIDC authentication. Regarding the Federated Learning server, this will enable securely managing tokens that clients will use to authenticate themselves with the server .

All the endpoints related to deployments are authenticated via OpenID Connect (OIDC) Access Tokens. We are using EGI production Check-In as OIDC Proxy service. Based on the Virtual Organization where the user belongs, we are able to send the job to predetermined namespaces in Nomad. The platform currently provides services for the following VOs: AI4EOSC, iImagine², and EGI Trainings. Being based on OIDC, this approach can also be extended to support the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service (INDIGO-IAM) in the future.

All the functionalities of the API have their corresponding integration tests to ensure further changes do not break existing expected functionalities. For more fine-grained details on the features, a Changelog is available in the Github repository [\[ai4-papi\]](#).

Finally, the API is expected to evolve in several ways. It will enable:

- A route to view different statistics concerning the use of the platform and the resources of the cluster. This will allow the Dashboard to show historic usage statistics and current cluster availability.
- A route to enable launching quick inference endpoints both to OSCAR [\[OSCAR\]](#) and Nomad.

2.1.2 - AI4EOSC Dashboard

AI4EOSC Dashboard

The AI4EOSC Dashboard [\[ai4-dashboard\]](#) is a modern single web application that provides a visual interface to the user, so that they can access the platform resources in an easy and user-friendly way.

It's been developed from scratch using robust web developer frameworks and tools, like Angular [\[Angular\]](#) and Jest [\[Jest\]](#) for the business logic and the Angular Material Component UI library to achieve a uniform and clean look both in desktop and mobile devices. The use of Angular enables a robust and dynamic

² Imagine is a sister project of AI4EOSC that exploits the software stack created within AI4EOSC to serve the Aquatic Science community. More information: <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

way to create the Dashboard by using components that are individually tested and can be reused, thus reducing code repetition and easing code maintenance.

The code relies on the use of Github actions to create a DevOps workflow that enables the quick additions of new features in a controlled and reproducible way. The two main tools used are the Release Please library³, to generate releases based on the Conventional Commits convention, and the build-and-push action, to automatically build images to DockerHub.

The Dashboard interacts with the API to retrieve the displayed information. It therefore has correspondingly two deployed instances: one for production and one for development.

The AI4EOSC Dashboard provides a public view for unauthenticated users and a private one for users logged via EGI Check-In AAI:

- Non-logged-in users can:
 - Explore the marketplace, which provides a complete relation of the available modules and tools (like the Federated Learning server) (see [Figure 3](#) for details).
 - Checking a module's detailed view, that shows additional information such as a description, the tags, links to the code repository, the docker image and even the dataset (if available).
 - Navigate through useful links in the sidebar.
- Logged-in users can, additionally:
 - Deploy a module via the Infrastructure Manager (IM).
 - Create a deployment with their specific hardware requirements filling a configuration form (see [Figure 4](#) for details).
 - View their current deployments (status, access endpoints, resources), as well perform actions over them (see [Figure 5](#) for details).

³ <https://github.com/googleapis/release-please>

Figure 3: Modules catalog view in the AI4EOsc Dashboard (logged-in user).

Figure 4: Deployment configuration in the AI4EOsc Dashboard.

The screenshot shows the AI4EOOSC Dashboard with the following data:

Name	Status	Container name	GPUs	Creation time (UTC)	Actions
AI4EOOSC prod - ML	running	deepfdc/deep-oc-generic-dev:latest	0	2024-02-05 16:35:09	[Stop] [Refresh] [Delete]
dasdadadasda	running	deepfdc/deep-oc-generic-dev:latest	0	2023-11-29 10:27:47	[Stop] [Refresh] [Delete]

Name	Status	Container name	GPUs	Creation time (UTC)	Actions
one with vscode	running	deepfdc/deep-oc-federated-server:tes	0	2023-12-20 12:39:04	[Stop] [Refresh] [Delete]
one with jupyter	running	deepfdc/deep-oc-federated-server:lat	0	2023-12-20 12:37:43	[Stop] [Refresh] [Delete]

Figure 5: User deployments view in the AI4EOOSC Dashboard.

In the future, the dashboard is expected to continue evolving to introduce new features such as:

- a section where the user will be able to check statistics of their deployments as well as cluster related statistics (e.g. available GPUs),
- a new option to the detailed module view, where unauthenticated users will be able to launch a quick inference endpoint to try the module via the Swagger interface, leveraging either OSCAR or Nomad resources,
- an improved module listing, allowing to filter by tags and show module framework icons (e.g. Tensorflow).

Plausible Analytics

As a way of gathering visitors information a Plausible instance was deployed [ai4-dashboard]. Plausible [Plausible] is an alternative to Google Analytics that is focused on privacy. It provides an easy to use dashboard where different usage metrics of the AI4EOOSC Dashboard are shown. To be compliant with GDPR regulations, a cookie consent banner is displayed on the AI4EOOSC Dashboard so users can opt out of being tracked by Plausible.

The Plausible instance is self-hosted at one of the partners datacenter (CSIC), so the data remains local, not depending on third parties. Plausible also preserves the privacy of the user by discarding information that could be used to identify a single user, for example the IP address that is used only when applying an algorithm to detect whether is a new user or not (to only log unique daily users).

The access to the Plausible statistics dashboard is private and works on an invitation basis, meaning that access has to be granted from one of the administrators of the platform.

2.1.3 - Composite AI tools

Composite AI tools represent a category of software and technologies designed to facilitate the integration and orchestration of multiple artificial intelligence (AI) models and machine learning techniques. Their primary function is to address complex challenges by combining diverse AI components into organized workflows. These tools act as intermediaries, fostering the collaborative operation of various AI models with the goal of achieving improved outcomes.

The objective is to implement visual programming tools that enable the creation of more intuitive inference models when working with pipelines and/or nodes. To accomplish this goal, Elyra [\[Elyra\]](#) and Node-RED [\[NodeRed\]](#) together with FlowFuse [\[Flowfuse\]](#) have been collaboratively employed. Despite their distinct functions and capabilities, both platforms share a common purpose in the utilization of composite AI tools. The code developed for all these tools can be found in the **ai4-compose** Github repository [\[ai4-compose\]](#).

Elyra

Elyra is an open-source platform that offers a comprehensive set of capabilities for streamlining AI workflow development. Built to work seamlessly with Jupyter notebooks, Elyra leverages the Python programming language, offering features such as visual pipeline composition, integrated access to tools and services, and an intuitive interface that simplifies the creation, modification, and execution of Python-based AI workflows. The recent publication of the tool for EGI Notebooks [\[EGI nb\]](#) further expands its accessibility.

In the context of Elyra, we have adopted a practical approach to leverage OSCAR services effectively. Specifically, we've created notebook files that utilize OSCAR's functionalities by integrating the OSCAR Python client [\[OSCAR py\]](#) to invoke and interact with OSCAR services. By obtaining the EGI token directly from within the notebook, we've enabled seamless access to OSCAR services that can run on remote locations. Furthermore, we have developed Python scripts to process and utilize the results, including visualizing, storing, and extracting additional information (e.g. using the *pytesseract* [\[Pytesseract\]](#) AI tool).

In addition to these technical implementations, we've also constructed illustrative pipelines as examples to demonstrate the Elyra's composition capabilities (see [Figure 6](#)).

Figure 6: Deployment of a pipeline in Elyra within the EGI notebook.

Node-RED & FlowFuse

Node-RED is a versatile open-source platform that empowers users with a wide array of capabilities for crafting and managing visual programming workflows. Node-RED is language-agnostic, providing flexibility in terms of the programming languages used. It also offers extensive integration possibilities with various data sources, IoT devices, and external services. Node-RED's marketplace allows users to access and install a multitude of modules, providing opportunities to improve existing processes or diversify workflows with ease.

Notably, we've facilitated the usage of Node-RED for multi-tenant usage by integrating FlowFuse. FlowFuse is a platform designed for deploying custom Node-RED instances, offering advanced capabilities for streamlining collaborative efforts. The platform includes pre-defined templates and modules, simplifying project deployment and configuration. This tool allows us to easily deploy and manage several instances of Node-RED in a centralized platform, as Node-RED is not multi-tenant.

We have developed a dedicated template for AI4EOSC projects, along with integrated modules. A project-wide instance of FlowFuse has been deployed [\[ai4-compose\]](#).

In Node-RED, we've developed practical modules (available in the [ai4-compose](#) repo) based on subflows. These subflows efficiently employ standard Node-RED nodes to make asynchronous requests to OSCAR services. Users can easily interact with these modules by providing essential details such as the endpoint, service name, and service token. For accessibility, we've made these modules available on the Node-RED marketplace [\[ai4-compose\]](#), allowing straightforward downloads through the Node-RED palette. Additionally, they can be obtained via the FlowFuse template for a more efficient integration process.

Moreover, we've crafted usage examples that comprise composite workflows, simplifying deployment and serving as valuable tutorials for Node-RED and OSCAR module utilization. These workflows incorporate nodes like "https request" for image downloads and "debug" nodes for result visualization, providing a practical approach for users to work with the outcomes effectively.

We illustrate both tools in [Figure 7](#) and [Figure 8](#).

Figure 7: Deployment of a workflow in Node-RED.

Figure 8: Applications and instances of Node-RED deployed in "Flows", AI4EOSC FlowFuse.

2.1.4 - Provenance tools

Provenance tools aim to improve the reproducibility and trustworthiness of the developed AI modules, by adhering to the FAIR principles.

In the context of the AI4EOSC project, the implementation of a provenance tracking system will provide semantic information to the user about:

- Entities: AI models and datasets.
- Activities: training and inference processes.
- Products: outputs generated using domain-specific vocabularies for each use-case.

Although the work on provenance tools is only due to start before this first release, we have already made progress on this task (especially regarding design and proof-of-concepts).

The system will be based on the W3C Resource Description Framework (RDF) standard [\[RDF\]](#) and the PROV-O ontology [\[PROV\]](#). Moreover, it will include a visualization tool, embedded in the experiment catalog entries, to enable an interactive inspection of the provenance graph.

The platform will dynamically generate RDF documents (using the JSON serializer) of the different entities and activities involved in an experiment. To do so, plain (non-semantic) JSON metadata documents will be mapped to RDF documents using the RDF Mapping Language (RML). A first implementation of the mappings approach used PROV-template [\[ai4-prov\]](#) but it is being migrated to RML due to its simplicity.

The RDF fragments will be stored in a key-value (URI-RDF) database. CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations over the database will be enabled through a REST API implemented in Java using the Spring Boot framework. A token-based authentication mechanism will be used.

The provenance visualizer will be implemented using React [\[React\]](#) and a graph library like D3.js [\[D3\]](#). It will be embedded in the experiment catalog using a simple IFRAME tag.

In order to implement the proposed solution, four different components are being implemented:

- **ai4-prov-generator**: generates RDF fragments that will compose the final provenance document. The connection with the metadata information exposed by MLflow is being considered.
- **ai4-prov-manager**: this component is responsible for:
 - management of RDF fragments exposed via a REST API,
 - plain JSON to RDF mapping,
 - RDF fragments chaining for building final provenance documents,
 - exposing final documents and querying using SparQL.
- **ai4-prov-viz**: this component is responsible for enabling an embeddable tool for interactive provenance analysis. A similar approach can be found in the Metaclip viewer [\[Metaclip\]](#) implemented by Predictia.
- **ai4-domain-ontologies**: domain-specific ontologies that will be used to describe the outputs of the different use-cases.

The first three components will be deployed in a single Docker image.

At the time of the First Release, the *prov-generator* and *prov-manager* components are in their final implementation stage and their integration in the AI4EOSC platform is being designed. The integration in the platform will require additional steps in the Jenkins pipelines (e.g. executed when a push command is executed in GitHub).

The development of *domain-ontologies* will start in February 2024 focusing on UC3 (automated thermography). The implementation of *prov-viz* will start once *prov-generator* and *prov-manager* are deployed.

2.1.5 - MLOps tools

MLOps is conceived as a set of practices to put and monitor AI applications in production. Based on the user requirements gathered in Deliverable 6.1 [D6.1], we are delivering two tools: one focusing on experiment tracking and another one focusing on drift detection [ai4-mlops].

MLflow

MLflow [MLflow] is a platform to streamline ML development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models.

Key features of the tool are:

- **MLflow Tracking:** tracking experiments to record and compare parameters and results;
- **MLflow Projects:** packaging ML code in a reusable and reproducible form in order to share with other data scientists or transfer to production;
- **MLflow Models:** managing and deploying models from a variety of ML libraries to multiple model serving and inference platforms;
- **MLflow Model Registry:** providing a central model store to collaboratively manage the full lifecycle of an MLflow Model, including model versioning, stage transitions and annotations.

In the context of AI4EOSC, we have deployed an MLflow tracking server primarily for experiment tracking [ai4-mlops]. We added an additional layer on top of the MLflow server that enables users to self-register in MLflow via the project common AAI (EGI Check-In) and to manage permissions to their experiments and models with other users. We implemented automatic backup of the in-use databases and enabled manual restore operations. The code related to the dockerized solution is available. The instance has the following configured databases (along with current usage metrics):

- **PostgresDB:** storing objects like experiments (#15), runs (#200), metrics (#3000), parameters (#2700), artifacts and registered models (#20). Actual artifacts such as models or datasets inputs consume a space of 29GB.

- **sqliteDB**: storing users (#15), permissions for experiments and registered models.

Once users authenticate to MLflow, they are able to view and modify their experiments and registered models (see the user interface displayed in [Figure 9](#)).

Figure 9: MLflow tracking server user interface.

With the feedback we have been gathering from early adopters, we have successfully deployed the instance into production [[ai4-mlops](#)]. We have published how-to tutorials in the project documentation [[ai4-docs](#)].

Frouros

Frouros is a drift detection tool for machine learning systems developed as part of this project [[ai4-mlops](#)].

Its main objective is to identify, during inference, any significant change in the previously learned concept by an AI model (concept drift), or changes related to the feature/covariate distributions (data drift) that can result in a notable decay in the model's performance. In this way, we can check if the AI model's predictions are not reliable anymore, due to some change between the relationship of the features and the target value (e.g. customer behavior change), if the data themselves changed or even if the dataset acquisition pipeline is failing (e.g. a faulty sensor). In any of these scenarios, it becomes imperative to retrain the model with updated data.

Implemented in Python, Frouros offers support for both concept drift and data drift detection. It contains a total of 32 detectors, including classic and some state-of-the-art detectors, thereby surpassing existing libraries in terms of the variety and number of implemented detectors.

Frouros prioritizes simplicity, offering easy-to-use tools to users through the following essential features:

- Datasets that can be used for testing purposes. They are divided into real or synthetic, depending on whether the dataset consists of real data or if that data has been artificially generated.
- Detectors: detection methods are organized into concept drift and data drift categories, based on the specific type of drift that needs to be identified.
- Callbacks: Frouros incorporates the concept of callbacks, a popular feature in ML libraries like PyTorch Lightning and Keras. This functionality enables users to execute custom code at key stages during the detector’s operation.
- Metrics: the tool also includes some evaluation metrics, such as prequential error metrics, designed to assess the performance of concept drift detectors.

3 - ROADMAP EVALUATION

This section evaluates how the roadmap stated in the Deliverable D5.1 “Implementation plan” has been realized so far, specifying when changes from the initial plan have occurred.

First, we take a look at the roadmap for the First Release of the components belonging to WP5, on [Table 1](#).

Component/Actions	Status + Description
AICompose / Design + Proof of Concept	● - The first prototype offers the ability to create graphical AI pipelines both in Elyra and Node-RED/Flowfuse, offering connectors with OSCAR to compose inference pipelines in a drag-and-drop approach.
Training API implementation	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), trainings are deployed as Nomad jobs.
Training database + API integration	● - Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of a training database was not deemed necessary (more info in Section 3.1).
Training API integration with WMS	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), it has the ability to manage deployments of Nomad jobs.
AI4EOSC Dashboard + Training + Exchange	● - A first prototype is successfully running in production, with the ability of serving a catalog of modules and tools (Exchange) as well as deploying them (Training).

Exchange API implementation	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), a diverse catalog of modules and tools is served to the user.
Exchange database + AI integration	● - Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of an exchange database was not deemed necessary at the time being (more info in Section 3.1).
New code repos	● - The work of moving to new (unified) repos has started but has not yet been completed (more info in Section 3.1).
New container registry	● - A new container registry has been created with Harbor, and Docker images are synced with DockerHub. [ai4-registry]
Interactive Development Environment	● - We have successfully integrated VScode and JupyterLab in the same Interactive Development Environment, deployable from the AI4EOSC Dashboard.

Table 1: Status of the roadmap for AI4EOSC 1. Color code: (●) for completed work, (●) for partially completed work, (●) for work that didn't need to be completed after reevaluation.

As shown, most of the roadmap for AI4EOSC release 1 has been successfully completed, with some minor actions still in the process of being completed.

3.1 - DEVIATION FROM THE INITIAL ROADMAP

In this section, we will give more context on the deviation from the initial Roadmap.

Regarding the actions in the Roadmap for AI4EOSC 1, we have deviated in the following actions:

- **Training database + API integration:** Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of a training database was not deemed necessary. We decided to rely instead on Nomad's own internal database, which has benefits in terms of the complexity of the code and overall architecture, thus improving maintainability.
- **Exchange database + AI integration:** Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of an exchange database was not deemed necessary at the time being, relying instead on the existing workflow of Jenkins and Github gitmodules repository. This provides benefits in terms of easier maintainability. Nevertheless, we are open to reconsider this in the future, if needed.
- **New code repos:** We are moving from the old module structure, to a unified format where both code and docker files are in a shared repo in the "ai4os-hub" Github organization [\[ai4-github\]](#). In the process, Jenkins pipelines will be refactored and metadata definition will be upgraded. To make this move transparent to users, all changes are being tested in the

development dashboard [[ai4-dashboard](#)]. This joint work with WP6 [D6.2] has progressed significantly but is not yet completely finished.

Regarding the roadmap for AI4EOSC release 2, we have already progressed in many actions, in advance of the promised schedule. This is shown in [Table 2](#). This sets us in a very good position to successfully tackle the second release.

Component/Actions	Description
AI4Compose / Implementation	Work has started, concluding the implementation and integration of Elyra into EGI Notebooks and completing the integration and deployment of FlowFuse.
Improved WMS Authentication	-
Model and data versionings	Work has started as we have already deployed the MLflow tool and are gathering feedback from the users.
Dashboard user centric tools	-
Automatic deployments to OSCAR	Work has already started as we are in the process of integrating OSCAR management in the API.
Drift monitoring tools	Work has already started with the first implementation of Frouros, which is stable and ready for use.
Model provenance	Work has already started by mapping JSON metadata to RDF using PROV templates.

Table 2: Status of the roadmap for AI4EOSC 2.

4 - CONCLUSION

This document outlines the status of the WP5 “Experiment Centric and Composite AI tools”, at the time of the First AI4EOSC Platform release.

In the document, the different WP5 components developed and improved during the project lifetime have been described, together with their current features. Furthermore, we have assessed that the status of the components is correctly aligned with the Roadmap defined in Deliverable 5.1.

By analyzing the results carried out in the present document, we can conclude that at the time of the AI4EOSC First Release, we have a robust set of tools already supporting users in their research activities. In the spirit of the Continuous Delivery workflow adopted by the project, we plan to incrementally

extend the functionality to the existing tools as well as adding new components and tools to the catalog.

REFERENCES

All references were accessed on Feb 21st 2024.

[ai4-docs] AI4EOSC documentation: <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/>

[ai4-compose] AI4EOSC Composite AI tools (★ WP5 component)

- Code - <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose> (release 1.0)
- Deployed development instance (FlowFuse) - <https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu/>
- Node-Red marketplace modules: <https://flows.nodered.org/user/Dialdroid>

[ai4-dashboard] AI4EOSC Dashboard (★ WP5 component)

- Code - <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard> (release 1.5.0)
- Docker image - <https://registry.services.ai4os.eu/ai4os/ai4eosc-dashboard>
- Deployed production instance - <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>
- Deployed development instance - <https://dashboard.dev.ai4eosc.eu/>
- Plausible instance - <https://stats.services.ai4os.eu/>

[ai4-github] Github repositories:

- AI4OS software stack - <https://github.com/ai4os>
- AI4OS AI modules and tools - <https://github.com/ai4os-hub>
- Old Deep-Hybrid-Datacloud software - <https://github.com/deephdc>

[ai4-mlops] AI4EOSC MLops tools (★ WP5 component)

- Code - <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-mlops/> (release 1.0)
- Code (MLflow) - <https://github.com/m-team-kit/mlflow-auth-gui/>
- Code (Frouros) - <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros>
- Deployed instance (MLflow) - <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

[ai4-papi] AI4EOSC Platform API (★ WP5 component)

- Code - <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi> (release 1.0)
- Docker image - <https://registry.services.ai4os.eu/ai4os/ai4-papi>
- Deployed production instance - <https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/docs>
- Deployed development instance - <https://api.dev.ai4eosc.eu/docs>

[ai4-prov] AI4EOSC provenance tools (★ WP5 component)

- Code (proof-of-concept): <https://github.com/danielsms/ai4-prov>

[ai4-registry] AI4EOSC container registry: <https://registry.services.ai4os.eu/> (★ WP5 component)

[ai4-storage] Ai4EOSC Nextcloud storage: <https://share.services.ai4os.eu>

[ai4eosc] AI4EOSC Platform. <https://ai4eosc.eu/>

[Angular] Angular: <https://angular.io/>

[D3] D3 JavaScript library: <https://d3js.org/>

[D5.1] Deliverable D5.1- Implementation plan: <https://zenodo.org/records/1164244>

[D6.1] Deliverable D6.1 - Analysis of user applications, collection of requirements: <https://zenodo.org/records/7635453>

[D6.2] Deliverable 6.2 - Intermediate status report about integration of pilot applications (not yet published)

[EGI nb] EGI notebooks: <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>

[Elyra] Elyra GitHub repository: <https://github.com/elyra-ai/elyra>

[FastAPI] Ramírez, S. FastAPI [Computer software]. <https://github.com/tiangolo/fastapi>

[Flowfuse] FlowFuse: <https://flowfuse.com/>

[Jest] Jest: <https://jestjs.io/>

[Metaclip] Metaclip: <http://metaclip.org>

[MLflow] MLflow, GitHub repository: <https://github.com/mlflow/mlflow/>

[NodeRed] NodeRed: <https://nodered.org/>

[Nomad] Nomad: <https://www.nomadproject.io/>

[React] React: <https://react.dev/>

[OpenAPI] OpenAPI Specification, GitHub repository: <https://github.com/OAI/OpenAPI-Specification>

[OSCAR] OSCAR: <https://oscar.grycap.net/>

[OSCAR py] OSCAR (Python), GitHub repository: https://github.com/grycap/oscar_python

[PROV] PROV Ontology: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

[RDF] Resource Description Framework (RDF): <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

[Plausible] Plausible: <https://plausible.io/>

[Pytesseract] Python Tesseract, GitHub repository: <https://github.com/madmaze/pytesseract>

[Vault] HashiCorp Vault: <https://www.vaultproject.io/>